

Figure S1. Plot of M2 shape vs. M2 Size in *G. rutlandae* (Black dots), *G. wesselsae* (Blue squares), *Galerix* sp. indet. from Potwar locality Y709 (purple cross), and *Galerix* sp.. indet. from Kulwanta locality K2, Ramnagar, India (Red star). Note that the Ramnagar specimen is larger than *G. rutlandae* despite exhibiting similar occlusal features. Compare with Fig. 3.2 as well.